

IMPACT RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH TOUGHENED EPOXY MATRICES

George Irven¹, Aaron Duncan¹, Emily Rolfe¹, Declan Carolan^{1,2}, Alexander Fergusson^{1,2} and John P. Dear¹

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Imperial College London, UK,
george.irven14@imperial.ac.uk, j.dear@imperial.ac.uk, www.imperial.ac.uk

² FAC Technology, London, UK,
declan@factechnology.com, alex@factechnology.com, www.factechnology.com

Keywords: Hybrid composites, Sandwich structures, Toughened epoxies

ABSTRACT

In the current work, high velocity impact tests were carried out on carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) epoxy composite sandwich structures containing an epoxy foam core. The effects of modifying the matrix of the CFRP laminate skins with polysiloxane core-shell rubber (CSR) nanoparticles and silica nanoparticles were investigated. The corresponding matrix formulations were manufactured into bulk polymer plates and CFRP laminate double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens. Of the bulk epoxy, tensile tests were used to evaluate modulus and ultimate tensile strength while single-edge-notched bend tests were employed to determine the fracture energy. The fracture energy of the bulk epoxy polymers increased from 188 J/m² for the unmodified polymer to a maximum of 4357 J/m² with the addition of 9 wt% of CSR nanoparticles. The steady-state propagation interlaminar fracture energy of the CFRP composites increased with increasing nanoparticle concentration, from 996 J/m² for the unmodified epoxy matrix to a maximum of 1678 J/m² with 9 wt% of CSR nanoparticles. The sandwich structures were impacted with an aluminium hemispherical projectile at 130 m/s. High speed cameras were used to obtain 3D digital image correlation (DIC) of the back face. The panels were sectioned and imaged after impact showing damage in the form of front skin perforation core crushing and cracks and rear skin-core delamination. Both the DIC data and imaging show notable differences between structures employing unmodified and modified matrices. Low amounts of CSR in the sandwich skin matrix improve back face deflection and delamination in the skin while increasing amounts lead to severe back face skin-core delamination.

1 INTRODUCTION

The combination of high specific strength, corrosion resistance and low radar signature make composite sandwich structures an attractive structural choice for many applications including in the naval sector. The characteristics of composite sandwich structures as naval hulls have many benefits including reduction of fuel and maintenance costs across the lifespan of the vessel [1]. However, the brittle nature of composite materials can lead to substantial overdesign of sandwich structure components, counteracting their weight and cost savings benefits. Naval vessels are unique, in that they have to withstand both structural loads as well as explosive blast and impact loadings. The toughness of a composite material, a critical parameter for a material to withstand blast loading, can be improved by improving the toughness of the individual components of the sandwich structure. Previous work by this group has demonstrated that by altering the layup of the individual plies in the composite skins, a significant increase in impact resistance of the structure can be obtained [2]. The research presented in this paper extends this concept and details a systematic study of the effect of increasing the toughness of the matrix material in the composite skins on the impact resistance of a sandwich structure. The transfer of toughness from the bulk polymer which acts as the matrix, through to a carbon fibre laminate and finally into the composite sandwich structure will be a central theme.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Materials

An amine-cured epoxy system formed the basis of all the materials investigated in the current work. The resin was a standard diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) with an epoxide equivalent weight of 185 g/eq. This was cured with a stoichiometric amount of a difunctional primary amine (JEFFAMINE D-230) from Huntsman. The silica, SiO₂, nanoparticles were obtained at 40 wt% in DGEBA, (Nanopox F400, Evonik). The silica nanoparticles used in the current work have a mean diameter of 20 nm [3]. The polysiloxane core-shell rubber CSR particles were also obtained at 40 wt% in DGEBA (Albidur EP2240A, Evonik) The average diameter of the CSR nanoparticles is 160 nm [3]. Low viscosity is a key attribute of a resin formulation when using resin infusion manufacturing methods. The low viscosity and slow cure rate of D-230 suited the current work well. It reduces the viscosity of the resin formulations when mixed and allowed the heating of the formulations prior to infusion to further reduce viscosity without the curing reaction undergoing exothermic runaway.

Seven formulations of epoxy resin with systematically increasing amounts of CSR nanoparticles and silica nanoparticles were prepared. The DGEBA epoxy resin was mixed with the epoxy containing the silica nanoparticles and the epoxy containing the CSR particles. These constituents were thoroughly mixed and degassed in a vacuum. A stoichiometric amount of the curing agent was then added, mixed and degassed again. Bulk polymer panels of each formulation were cast by pouring the resin mixture into silicone moulds to produce either 3 mm or 8 mm thick plates from which bulk specimen test samples could be machined. The plates were cured at 30 °C for 10 h, followed by a 12 h post-cure at 70 °C. Carbon fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite panels and full sandwich structures were manufactured using resin infusion. CFRP double cantilever beam panels adopted a layup of 16 sheets of bi-axial non-crimp carbon fibre, while the sandwich structures used 4 sheets for each skin. The composite and sandwich structure panels were laid up on a flat, vacuum-assisted heated resin-infusion tool, and sealed using a vacuum bag. The infusion then took place over a period of 5-10 min depending on the viscosity and then cured under vacuum for 10 h at 50 °C. The panel was then post-cured at 70 °C for a further 12 h at atmospheric pressure. The sandwich panels were 230 mm × 230 mm in size and employed a 30 mm thick epoxy foam core. The epoxy foam core used had a nominal density of 170 kg/m³ and was manufactured using PB170 foaming epoxy resin and DM03 amine-based hardener provided by Sicomin. The foaming took place in an open 300 mm × 300 mm aluminium mould lined with a self-adhesive polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) coated glass fabric. The mould was situated in a temperature-controlled environment at 21.5 °C and all foam was made according to the manufacturer's guidelines. When used in the sandwich structures and for uniaxial compression testing, the foam was CNC milled to obtain flat faces and remove any skin formed at the mould surfaces during the foaming process.

Formulations for the current work include a control sample of pure DGEBA and 3, 6, and 9 wt% of CSR. The addition of CSR was expected to reduce the modulus of the resin system [4]. The expected reduction in modulus was predicted using the Halpin-Tsai model, a semi-empirical model that allows the calculation of Young's modulus of a composite given the properties of the constituent phases [5]. The model calculates the tensile modulus, E_t , of a composite as follows:

$$E_t = \frac{1 + \zeta\eta V_f}{1 - \eta V_f} E_m \quad (1)$$

Where E_m is the modulus of the matrix, V_f is the volume fraction of the particulate phase, ζ is a shape factor and where:

$$\eta = \frac{E_f/E_m - 1}{E_f/E_m + \zeta} \quad (2)$$

The shape factor, ζ , has no direct physical significance, which is one of the major criticisms of this model. However, Halpin and Kardos [6] recommend a shape factor of $\zeta = 2$ for spherical particles, which is used for all the present predictions of the moduli of the nanocomposites.

The significant drop in modulus caused by the introduction of rubber into the matrix of a CFRP laminate will have an adverse effect on matrix-dominated properties such as out-of-plane modulus. The current work explores whether the toughening benefits of CSR can be maintained whilst eliminating the reduction in modulus through the simultaneous addition of silica nanoparticles. To calculate the required wt% of silica, a modified Halpin-Tsai model as used by Carolan et al [3] was employed. The ‘cascaded application of a standard two-phase homogenisation procedure’ allows the calculation of a composite modulus containing two particulate phases. The modified model considers a system of unit volume containing a matrix of volume fraction, v_m , and two types of spherical inclusions, with volume fractions, v_1 and v_2 respectively. The first step separates the composite into two separate regions, A and B, such that each region contains a matrix phase, volume fraction v_m as in the original volume, and one type of particle, volume fraction $(1 - v_m)$. Each of these regions can be homogenised using the Halpin-Tsai model. The volume fractions to be use in the final homogenisation, v_A and v_B are dictated by conservation of volume as: $v_A(1 - v_m) = v_1$.

2.2 Methods

Tensile tests were conducted on the seven formulations to determine the uniaxial tensile stress versus strain curves in accordance with ISO-527 [7]. Dumbbell specimens with a gauge length of 30mm were machined directly from 3 mm cast plates. The tests were carried out at a constant crosshead displacement rate of 1 mm/min. A clip-gauge extensometer was utilised to directly measure the strain in the test specimen. At least five replicate tests for each formulation were carried out to study the repeatability of the results.

Single-edge notched bending (SENB) tests in three-point bend configuration were conducted to determine the plane-strain fracture toughness, K_{Ic} , and fracture energy, G_{Ic} , in accordance with ASTM D-5045 [8]. Test specimens of dimensions 80 mm \times 16 mm \times 8 mm were machined from the cast plates. These specimens were pre-notched to a depth of 6 mm before subsequent tapping of the notch to produce a sharp crack to a depth of \approx 8 mm using a liquid nitrogen chilled razor blade. Testing was conducted using a screw-driven universal testing machine at a constant crosshead displacement rate of 1 mm/min. The fracture toughness was calculated via:

$$K_{Ic}(\text{bulk}) = \frac{P}{bw^{1/2}} f\left(\frac{a}{w}\right) \quad (3)$$

where P is the load at failure, b and w are the sample thickness and width, respectively, and $f(a/w)$ is a fitting function depending on the crack length, a . The fracture energy, G_{Ic} was calculated using the energy method via:

$$G_{Ic}(\text{bulk}) = \frac{U}{bw\phi} \quad (4)$$

Where U is the energy under the corrected load-displacement curve and ϕ is an energy calibration factor as defined in the ASTM standard [8]. At least five replicate specimens were tested for each formulation.

Fracture toughness tests of the CFRP composites were conducted using DCB specimens in accordance with ISO-15024 [9]. Test specimens of 200 \times 20 \times 4 mm³ were machined from composite panels. A 12 μ m thick PTFE crack starter film of length 50 mm was used to ensure an appropriately sharp starter crack. The corrected beam theory (CBT) method was employed to calculate both the mode-I initiation interlaminar fracture energy, $G_{Ic,init}$, and the steady-state propagation fracture energy, $G_{Ic,prop}$, of the composites. The interlaminar fracture energy was calculated via:

$$G_{Ic[init,prop]}(comp) = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + |\Delta|)} \frac{F}{N} \quad (5)$$

where P is the load, δ is the displacement, a the crack length and b is the width of the specimen. The terms F and N are correction factors for large displacements and the presence of the load blocks, respectively. Finally, the term Δ is a correction factor to account for the fact that the DCB beam is not perfectly built-in.

The tests were conducted at a constant crosshead displacement rate of 2 mm/min using a screw-driven tensile testing machine. The loads and displacements were recorded, and the crack lengths monitored using a travelling microscope. At least five replicate specimens were tested for each formulation of composite matrix. An R-curve was observed from the measured data, i.e. the value of the interlaminar fracture energy increased as the crack steadily propagated through the CFRP DCB test: from value for the onset, or initiation, of crack growth until an upper limit, steady-state value of the interlaminar fracture energy for crack propagation was attained. Thus, an initiation value, $G_{Ic,init}(comp)$, for the onset of crack growth and a value for steady-state propagation, $G_{Ic,prop}(comp)$, could be defined, as described in ISO-15024 [9]. (The value of $G_{Ic,init}(comp)$ was taken at the onset of nonlinearity of the load versus displacement curve during the first initial loading step, as defined in ISO-15024 [9].)

High velocity impact experiments were performed using a gas gun apparatus accelerating a hemispherical aluminium projectile, as used by Rolfe et al. [2]. The velocity of the projectile was recorded by two infrared sensors located towards the end of the gas gun barrel exit. The panel was contained within a polycarbonate and aluminium safety box and two high-speed cameras were located behind the panel outside of the safety box. These cameras recorded at 28630 frames per second (fps) with a resolution of 192×440 , corresponding to a $65 \times 150 \text{ mm}^2$ area on the back of the panels. To facilitate digital image correlation (DIC), the panels were spray painted matt white and a random black speckle pattern was applied to the back surface of the panel.

Imaging of the fracture samples and impacted sandwich structures was conducted. A field-emission gun scanning-electron microscope (FEG-SEM) was used to obtain high-resolution images of the fracture surfaces of both the SENB and DCB samples. An accelerating voltage of between 3 and 5 kV was applied. The samples were sputter coated with a 5 nm layer of gold-palladium, prior to examination, to prevent charging of the material. The sandwich structures contained the projectile beneath the first skin after impact, the projectile could not be retrieved without damaging the skin further. As a result, a low viscosity epoxy resin containing a blue dye was poured into the impact site to surround the projectile and protect the damage in the panel from being exaggerated during cutting. The panels were then cut to expose the center line and a 45° line of the panel using a diamond edge table saw as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of cuts made in sandwich panels and an example of an impacted panel.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Imaging Study

Figure 2 displays micrographs of the fracture surfaces of two bulk epoxy SENB samples. Figure 2a contains 9 wt % CSR and 17.2 wt % silica nanoparticles. The CSR particles are indicated as large voids whereas the silica nanoparticles can be observed as smaller white spots highlighted in red circles. It is clear from Figure 2a that the diameters of the cavitated CSR particles are significantly larger than the original 160 nm average. This indicates that void growth has taken place during the fracture of the sample, a well-established toughening mechanism in rubber modified epoxy [10]. Significant crack branching and feathering on the surface is clear in Figure 2a, unlike the smooth surface of an unmodified epoxy sample. Figure 2b contains 6 wt % CSR and serves to demonstrate that the CSR particles are well-dispersed within the epoxy and that there were no problems with clustering of nanoparticles.

Figure 2 also shows the typical fracture surfaces of two CFRP DCB samples employing modified matrices. Figure 2c contains 9 wt % CSR particles which can be observed as white spots or dark voids in the matrix. This image (from left to right) contains a partially covered fibre, exposed fibre, and empty fibre track. The empty track exhibits how CSR particles can line up against the fibre surface and enable more fibre pull-out and bridging, thus increasing toughness. Figure 2d shows the space between two fibres of a 3 wt % CSR and 5.9 wt % silica nanoparticle sample. The image demonstrates the limited space between some fibres, as a result, there is less possibility for void growth and cavitation of the CSR particles. The cavitated CSR particles in this image, highlighted by red circles, are much smaller than those of the bulk epoxy in Figure 2a. Thus, partially limiting the transferability of toughness from a bulk epoxy to its corresponding CFRP laminate.

Figure 2: Fracture surfaces of bulk SENB samples containing (a): 9 wt % CSR and 17.2 wt % silica nanoparticles. (b): 6 wt % CSR at a lower magnification. Fracture surfaces of CFRP composites with matrices containing (c): 9 wt % CSR and (d): 3 wt % CSR and 5.9 wt % silica nanoparticles.

3.2 Bulk Tensile Properties

The tensile properties of the bulk epoxy polymers are summarised in Table 1. It can be seen from Figure 3a that the addition of increasing CSR nanoparticles caused an approximately linear drop in the tensile modulus measured. This drop is more severe than that predicted by the Halpin Tsai model for this resin system. Similar disparities between model predictions and results were noted by Carolan et al. [3]. The addition of silica nanoparticles to the CSR modified bulk epoxy polymers was observed to cause an increase in measured modulus. As described in the materials section, the predicted modulus for the three silica and CSR modified systems were calculated to match that of the unmodified epoxy polymer. However, the measured moduli were found to be below that of the unmodified system, again the model has under predicted the effect of CSR on the modulus. A higher silica wt % would be required to fully recover the modulus of the unmodified system.

Figure 3b shows the ultimate tensile strength properties of the bulk epoxy polymers. In all cases, the strength decreased approximately linearly with increasing CSR content, while the addition of silica nanoparticles had no effect on the experimentally measured strength.

wt % CSR	wt % SiO ₂	E _{exp} [GPa]	E _{pred} [GPa]	% Error	UTS [MPa]
0	0	3.83 ± 0.12	-	-	73.1 ± 0.005
3	0	3.51 ± 0.14	3.63	-3.3	62.8 ± 0.005
6	0	3.16 ± 0.07	3.45	-8.4	59.6 ± 0.007
9	0	2.78 ± 0.05	3.26	-15	52.0 ± 0.009
3	5.9	3.45 ± 0.13	3.83	-9.9	63.8 ± 0.006
6	11.7	3.50 ± 0.19	3.83	-8.6	57.5 ± 0.013
9	17.2	3.67 ± 0.22	3.83	-4.2	51.8 ± 0.017

Table 1: Tensile properties of the bulk epoxy polymers.

Figure 3: Tensile properties of the bulk epoxy polymers. (a): Modulus vs CSR content with the dashed lines representing Halpin-Tsai predictions. (b): ultimate tensile strength vs CSR content.

3.3 Fracture Properties

The fracture energy, G_{Ic} , of each of the bulk polymers is given in both Figure 4a and Table 2. The addition of CSR nanoparticles to the epoxy resin was found to greatly increase the toughness of the bulk resin. While the silica nanoparticles had a comparatively insignificant effect. Liang and Pearson [11], Kinloch et al. [12], Carolan et al [13], and Incerti et al. [4] have noted that the toughness of epoxy polymers is enhanced by the addition of either silica nanoparticles or rubber particles.

The measured values of the mean mode-I initiation, $G_{Ic,init}(comp)$, and propagation, $G_{Ic,prop}(comp)$, inter-laminar fracture energies are also given in Table 2 and Figures 5a and 5b. The benefits of nano-modification of the composite matrices can be clearly observed, as the CFRP composites with the modified epoxy matrices exhibit significantly higher values of both the initiation, $G_{Ic,init}(comp)$ and the steady-state propagation, $G_{Ic,prop}(comp)$, interlaminar fracture energies. From these tests, the transfer of toughness from the bulk polymer to the CFRP laminate is clear. However, there is a limit to the effectiveness of the toughening of a CFRP laminate as discussed by Carolan et al. [3] where by the toughening mechanisms of the nanoparticles ahead of the crack tip, such as void growth, are restricted by the nearby fibres. For a 9 wt% CSR system, the values of G_{Ic} in the bulk polymer reach 4357 ± 590 J/m², whereas in the composite the matrix dominated value of $G_{Ic,init}(comp)$ only reaches 661 ± 112 J/m². The values of $G_{Ic,prop}(comp) - G_{Ic,init}(comp)$ are plotted in Figure 4b. Calculating the difference between propagation and initiation should remove the effect of matrix toughness, however, Figure 4b shows an increase in $G_{Ic,prop}(comp) - G_{Ic,init}(comp)$ for increasing CSR content. As a result, it can be said that the increasing presence of CSR particles increases the fibre-induced toughening mechanisms such as fibre-bridging. It can be seen from Figure 2c that CSR particles often line the empty fibre tracks on a DCB fracture surface. The presence of CSR reduces the area of matrix in contact with the fibre thus more easily allowing the fibre to be pulled out and form a bridge or fibre-bundle bridge. It can be seen, as with the bulk polymers, that the effect of CSR dominates that of the silica which has a comparatively insignificant effect.

wt% CSR	wt% SiO ₂	$G_{Ic}(bulk)$ [J/m ²]	$G_{Ic,init}(comp)$ [J/m ²]	$G_{Ic,prop}(comp)$ [J/m ²]
0	0	188 ± 37	406 ± 61	996 ± 44
3	0	2695 ± 41	432 ± 33	1314 ± 169
6	0	2790 ± 318	613 ± 149	1534 ± 111
9	0	4357 ± 590	661 ± 112	1678 ± 104
3	5.9	2139 ± 408	537 ± 88	1411 ± 138
6	11.7	2922 ± 104	617 ± 130	1566 ± 49
9	17.2	4085 ± 549	670 ± 44	1643 ± 72

Table 2: Measured fracture energies of both the bulk epoxy polymers and the CFRP laminates.

Figure 4: Fracture energies vs wt % of CSR. (a): Bulk epoxy polymers. (b): Propagation -initiation for CFRP laminates.

Figure 5: Fracture energies vs wt % of CSR. (a): Initiation for CFRP laminates. (b): Propagation for CFRP laminates.

3.4 Impact Study

Table 3 displays a summary of the data from the impact study. Figure 6 shows the out of plane displacement for all the panels under impact at $130 \pm 3 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ with a $28.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ g}$ hemispherical aluminium projectile. Figure 7 displays the back-face velocity versus time for all panels calculated from the out of plane displacement DIC data. The point where the front skin was perforated by the projectile can be seen in Figure 6 as the inflection point at 0.25 ms on the rise to maximum displacement. The perforation point is prominent when observing the velocity versus time graph as a dip at 0.25 ms. Perforation can also be viewed as the central section displacement in Figure 8 transitions from a smooth maximum displacement to a more angular maximum displacement. Figure 9a displays the maximum displacement versus wt % CSR, the unmodified panel experiences a large displacement due to less energy being absorbed through skin damage. The 3 wt % CSR toughened panels have a lower displacement; however, further additions of CSR increase displacement due to the further drop in modulus of the matrix resin. The subsequent addition of silica nanoparticles helps to reduce the displacement to levels similar to that of the 3% CSR modified panel. Given the layup of the skins have fibre in only the 0 and 90 directions, the deflection of the panels may have an appreciable dependence on the matrix modulus, as a result these findings relating to panel displacements can be expected.

wt% CSR	wt% SiO ₂	Projectile Mass [g]	Projectile Velocity [ms^{-1}]	Maximum Displacement [mm]	Maximum Velocity [ms^{-1}]	Delamination Extent [mm]
0	0	28.4	130	10.5	37.1	43.8
3	0	28.4	132	8.6	19.2	40.9
6	0	28.4	128	10.6	37.9	36.0
9	0	28.5	132	11.2	41.8	34.8
3	5.9	28.3	130	9.0	24.9	35.9
6	11.7	28.4	127	9.1	25.1	38.7
9	17.2	28.5	132	9.6	30.7	35.7

Table 3: A summary of the data collected from the impact study.

Figure 6: Centre point displacement vs time for all sandwich structures.

Figure 7: Centre point velocity vs time for all sandwich structures.

Prior to perforation the panels behave uniformly, however, the initial dip in velocity, maximum velocity and maximum out of plane displacement allow for more informative analysis. From Figure 7, a large initial dip in velocity corresponds well to a greater maximum velocity later. The panels that provide less resistance to the projectile transfer less load to the back skin, and so a large dip in velocity occurs at 0.25 ms. These panels then undergo larger back-face deflection as the projectile makes direct contact with the rear skin with a higher velocity. Figure 10 displays a section of the impact site of a panel and the damage types that take place during perforation of the front skin. The energy absorbed during perforation of the front skin occurs via four identifiable mechanisms: fibre breaking, delamination in the skin, delamination of the skin from the core and core crushing. Toughening of the matrix is most likely to affect the extent of delamination within the skin itself, as such, this was measured using high resolution images, the results are presented in Table 3 and Figure 9b. Increasing the toughness

has reduced the delamination within the skin as observed from the section cut. Once the projectile has passed through the front skin, energy is then absorbed through further core-crushing and cracks and, in some cases, the delamination of the back face from the core. It is unclear if the cracks in the core take place as the projectile impacts the front skin and are shear induced, or if they are due the excessive back face deflection putting the core in tension.

Figure 8: Deflection at time intervals for the vertical centre section of the sandwich structure with an unmodified matrix. (a): Up to maximum displacement. (b): Return from maximum to minimum displacement.

Figure 9: (a): Maximum out-of-plane displacement vs wt % CSR (b): Maximum panel velocity vs maximum displacement.

Figure 11 shows two panel cross sections, the unmodified panel and a 9 wt % CSR modified panel. The main observation between these two panels, both of which underwent similar back face deflection, is that the 9 wt % CSR panel trades increased core cracking for widespread back face skin-core delamination. Significant differences between the modulus and UTS of the two matrix resins used could be affecting the interfacial strength between the skin and core. This is a similar phenomenon as to when CSR in a CFRP DCB sample causes increased fibre pullout but on a macroscopic level. The bond strength between the skin and the core is governed by the properties of the matrix resin, indeed the results suggest that the strength and not the toughness of the resin is the dominating factor.

Figure 10: Image of impact site of sandwich structure with matrix containing 3 wt % CSR.

Figure 11: Typical images of sandwich structure cross sections with blue resin reservoir on top. (a) Unmodified matrix. (b) 9 wt % CSR modified matrix.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions derived from this work are as follows:

- The addition of CSR nanoparticles in the resin system used caused a decrease in modulus beyond the values obtained from the Halpin-Tsai model. The silica nanoparticles went some way to restoring the modulus to that of the unmodified system. The addition of CSR caused a drop in UTS while silica nanoparticles had little effect.
- The addition of CSR nanoparticles caused a significant increase in the fracture energies of bulk epoxy polymers while silica nanoparticles had a comparatively insignificant effect.
- The use of CSR modified matrices was demonstrated to significantly enhance the Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness of CFRP laminates. The transfer of toughness from the bulk epoxy polymers to the CFRP laminates in the form of initiation interlaminar fracture energies was limited due to space constraints between fibres. However, the steady-state propagation interlaminar fracture energies were enhanced through increasing CSR content as increased levels of fibre-bridging were induced.
- The addition of 3 wt % CSR to the matrix of a sandwich structure reduced back-face deflection and delamination within the front skin. Increasing to 6 and 9 wt % CSR caused increased deflection due to excessive drop in modulus outweighing toughening effects. The subsequent addition of silica nanoparticles mitigated this drop in modulus and reduced deflection. The addition of 6 and 9 wt % CSR also caused large rear face skin-core delamination.

Future work will concentrate on the bond between skin and core, and the effect of altering core properties.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Dr Yapa Rajapakse of ONR is very much acknowledged for supporting Dr Emily Rolfe for her PhD on blast performance of hybrid composite materials. Declan Carolan would like to acknowledge the financial support of Marie Curie Actions under the Society & Enterprise Fellowship scheme.

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